

Moisture Effects on Impact Strength and Recovery in Carbon Fiber Reinforced Vitrimers

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Utilization of Composites

Driving Factors for Utilization of Composites

- ❑ For future mobility to integrate with existing infrastructure, lightweight components are required for maximized driving range
- ❑ Pressure is placed on car manufacturers to satisfy legal regulations to alleviate greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions

Potential of Composites

- ❑ In 2021, composites market was valued at \$88.8 billion, and the market is forecasted to expand to \$144.5 billion by 2028
- ❑ With composition of metals for automobiles being 63% by weight, 10% weight reduction can increase fuel efficiency by 6-10%

Property	Thermoset	Thermoplastic	Vitrimer
Strength	High (crosslinked network)	Moderate to High	High (similar to thermoset)
Reshapability	✗ Permanent shape after cure	✓ Heat-softenable and reshaped	✓ Reprocessable via bond exchange (no melting)
Repairability	✗ Difficult; requires scarfing + long thermal cycles	✗ Poor; needs melting and reprocessing	✓ Fast healing via heat/stimulus; no structural prep needed
Recyclability	✗ Incineration or grinding (energy-intensive, fiber loss)	✓ Re-meltable and reusable	✓ Chemically recyclable; enables clean fiber separation for reuse

Vitrimers: A New Matrix for Composites

What Are Vitrimers?

- ❑ A specific class of polymer materials with dynamic covalent bonds for reversible cross-linking
- ❑ Discovered in 2011 by French researcher Ludwik Leibler

Key Characteristics of Vitrimers

- ❑ Like thermosets, can crosslink at certain temperatures
- ❑ Like thermoplastics, can be softened and reformed at higher temperatures

Vitrimers in Composite Manufacturing

- ❑ Vitrimers can be used to make fiber reinforced composites
- ❑ Potential to use reversible cross-linking ability for efficient material recycling

Problem Statement

- ❑ Vitrimer composites offer self-healing and reshaping, but impact behavior remains underexplored
- ❑ Existing studies neglect real-world factors like moisture exposure (e.g., seawater, humidity)
- ❑ Environmental moisture can degrade composite properties by lowering impact strength
- ❑ Current protection methods (coatings) are vulnerable to aging or mechanical damage
- ❑ Repairability post-environmental aging is unclear, especially for fiber-reinforced vitrimers.

Fabrication of Vitrimer Composites

- **Reinforcement Types:** Milled (60 μm), Forged (6 mm), and Woven (3K fabric) carbon fibers used at 8%, 15%, and 40% V_f
- **Resin System:** Vitrimax T100™ epoxy + hardener; hardener preheated at 80 °C for 2 h
- **Milled, Forged CFRV:** Fibers dispersed in epoxy, hardener added, degassed at 1 MPa for 1 min
- **Woven CFRV:** 12 layers (259.2 g) for 40% V_f
- **Molding:** Compression molded at 130 °C, 0.8 MPa for 4 h in 300 × 300 × 4 mm mold

Impact Testing

- **Equipment:** QM700A digital tester with 1.114 kg pendulum, 0.3 m arm
- **Specimens:** 80 × 10 × 4 mm, tested in edgewise parallel and flatwise normal orientations
- **Purpose:** Edgewise simulates interlaminar failure; flatwise tests through-thickness resistance.

$$v = \sqrt{2gH}$$

$$H = L_p \left(1 - \cos \theta_i \frac{\pi}{180} \right)$$

$$E = mgL_p \left(\cos \theta_f \frac{\pi}{180} - \cos \theta_i \frac{\pi}{180} \right)$$

Environmental Conditioning

□ **Pre-conditioning:** All specimens oven-dried at 50 °C for 24 h to set dry mass baseline

□ **Aging Protocols:**

- Seawater: Immersion at 25 °C and 50 °C using synthetic salt mix (~33.3 g/L)
- Humidity: 90% Relative Humidity (RH) at 25 °C and 50 °C per ISO 6270-2 CH standard

□ **Fickian Modeling:** 10-term Fickian diffusion series; D extracted via nonlinear least-squares fit (MATLAB)

□ **Key Estimate:** $t_{95\%} \approx 19$ days (25 °C), 2 days (50 °C) for 4 mm thickness.

Material Type	Environment	Temperature (°C)	RH (%)	Duration (h)
Milled, Forged, Woven	Seawater Immersion	25, 50	–	1, 2, 4, 24, 48, 72
Milled, Forged, Woven	Humidity Exposure	25, 50	90	1, 2, 4, 24, 48, 72

$$\frac{M(t)}{M_{\infty}} = 1 - \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{8}{\pi^2(2n+1)^2} \exp\left(-\frac{\pi^2(2n+1)^2Dt}{4h^2}\right)$$

$$\frac{M(t)}{M_{\infty}} \approx 1 - \frac{8}{\pi^2} \exp\left(-\frac{\pi^2Dt}{4h^2}\right) \quad t_{95\%} \approx \frac{4h^2}{\pi^2D}$$

$$D(T) = D^0 \exp\left(-\frac{E_a}{RT}\right)$$

Effect of Orientation on Impact Damage

- Milled Composites: Very low impact strength (4.1 kJ/m² flat, 2.3 kJ/m² edge); brittle fracture due to short, random 7 μm fibers.
- Forged Composites: Moderate strength (~18.5/16.7 kJ/m²); isotropic behavior with delamination and full fiber breakage.
- Woven Composites: Highest strength (~128.6/115.6 kJ/m²); flatwise impact resisted better due to fiber face exposure.
- Fracture Observations:
 - Flatwise: partial fiber fracture + bulging → high energy absorption
 - Edgewise: fiber pull-out, interlayer fracture

Moisture Uptake of Carbon Fiber Reinforced Vitrimer Composites

- Milled, forged, and woven CFRVs aged in 25 °C/50 °C under humidity (90% RH) and seawater immersion.
- **Fickian Fit Results:** humidity $D \uparrow$ with T , seawater D showed anomalies (25 °C > 50 °C in some cases).
- Seawater → faster uptake than humidity
- 50 °C → higher total absorption despite some lower D values
- *Forged CFRVs:* Highest uptake (~3.8%) due to voids and microcracks → capillary-driven diffusion.
- Early-time D estimates affected by microgram-scale fluctuations; trends remain consistent and meaningful.

Type	Condition	Temperature (°C)	D (m ² /s)
Milled	Humidity	25	1.19×10^{-11}
		50	1.57×10^{-11}
	Seawater	25	1.94×10^{-11}
		50	1.87×10^{-11}
Forged	Humidity	25	1.47×10^{-11}
		50	1.50×10^{-11}
	Seawater	25	1.91×10^{-11}
		50	1.64×10^{-11}
Woven	Humidity	25	2.07×10^{-11}
		50	2.37×10^{-11}
	Seawater	25	2.34×10^{-11}
		50	1.57×10^{-11}

Effect of Moisture on Impact Damage

Humidity Exposure

- ❑ Sharp declines after 4 h; no recovery observed at 72 h
- ❑ Milled: -81.4%, Forged: -65.7%, Woven: -54.0% (4 h vs. 24 h)

Seawater Immersion

- ❑ Initial drop (4–24 h), followed by partial recovery at 72 h
- ❑ Milled: -40.6%, Forged: -58.1%, Woven: -11.9% (4 h vs. 24 h)
- ❑ Recovery attributed to moisture-induced plasticization enhancing ductility and energy absorption.

Fracture Observation

- ❑ • Forged: surface degradation, mold-like appearance
- ❑ • Woven: multilayer fractures, visible resin flow with time

Effect of Moisture on Impact Damage

Milled

- T_g ↑ from 91.5 °C (dry) → 102 °C (humidity)
- T_g ↓ to 90.5 °C (seawater); large endothermic peak → plasticization dominant

Forged

- T_g consistently ↑ from 101.9 °C → 108.2 °C (humidity) → 116.1 °C (seawater)
- Suggests post-curing or plasticizer loss, leading to stiffer network

Woven

- T_g ↑ to 110 °C (humidity), then ↓ to 94.6 °C (seawater)
- Indicates initial curing, followed by strong plasticization due to deep moisture ingress

Note: Deepest endothermic peaks in seawater → confirms high moisture absorption and enthalpic relaxation

Effect of Moisture on Recovery from Impact

Milled CFRV

- ❑ High recovery (89–111%) across all conditions → resilient structure
- ❑ Seawater-induced voids seen, but minimal strength loss

Forged CFRV

- ❑ Excellent dry recovery (125%) from heat-press compaction
- ❑ Seawater severely reduced recovery (~38%) → fiber–matrix debonding
- ❑ Humidity: moderate recovery (77–85%)

Woven CFRV

- ❑ Limited dry recovery (61%); no recovery post moisture → fiber fracture irreversible
- ❑ **Oven-Drying:** Removed moisture (0.3–2.2% mass loss), but did not restore mechanical integrity → damage is structural, not just moisture retention
- ❑ **Fracture Surfaces:** Seawater → more porosity; woven → visible delamination and unrecoverable breakage

Conclusions

- Moisture exposure significantly degrades impact strength, especially under prolonged seawater or humidity at elevated temperatures.
- Forged CFRVs absorbed the most moisture, leading to severe mechanical deterioration due to voids and microcracks.
- Woven CFRVs showed irreversible damage post-immersion, with minimal repair recovery due to continuous fiber fracture.
- Milled CFRVs exhibited the most stable performance, showing high recovery and low moisture uptake.
- T_g shifts revealed competing effects of plasticization and post-curing, influenced by fiber type and environment.

THANK YOU FOR LISTENING

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